

LONG-TERM INTERFACIAL BOND BEHAVIOUR OF CARBON-FIBRE TEXTILE REINFORCED CEMENTITIOUS MORTAR

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ABSTRACT

Interfacial debonding is one of the key failure modes in carbon fibre textile reinforced cementitious mortar (TRCM) under marine environment, therefore the long-term interfacial degradation of TRCM submerged in seawater is experimentally investigated in this study. The moisture-induced degradation has been targeted, particularly on the effects of hygroscopic expansion and interfacial ageing. In order to accelerate the ageing process, elevated temperature ageing treatment were adopted in this study. It is found that accelerated ageing can reduce the pull-out performance by nearly half when it is immersed under 60 °C, whilst the reduction can be neglected at 20 °C.

KEYWORDS

Textile reinforced cementitious mortar (TRCM); interfacial debonding; marine environment; accelerated ageing treatment.

INTRODUCTION

Infrastructures, including those located in offshore areas, are usually designed to have a service life for 50 years or longer (Fergani, 2017; Uthaman et al., 2020). However, the history of widely applying FRP reinforced mortar to the construction industry is no more than this time span (Fergani, 2017; Matthys & Triantafillou, 2001). Consequently, if degradation data collected from existent FRP reinforced structures was the only information to study their long-term behaviour in natural environments, it would not be feasible to investigate their durability performance throughout the whole service life. On the other hand, experimental methods used to explore the ageing behaviour of FRP composite are usually limited to the finite period, thereby unrealistic to simulate the material ageing in normal service conditions. Therefore, elevated-temperature accelerated ageing is a commonly used approach to study the durability of FRP reinforced mortar within a limited duration (Ahmed, Guo, Zhang, Shi, & Zhu, 2020; Duo, Liu, Liu, Tafsirojjaman, & Sabbrojjaman, 2021; Gravina, Li, Smith, & Visintin, 2020).

The material ageing is actually the result of molecular movements and microstructure changes which damage the material integrity, particular at the interface. Within a certain range, raising temperature can facilitate the current molecular motions and thus accelerate the material ageing process. Many experimental investigations into accelerated ageing of FRP reinforced mortar demonstrated that increasing the ambient temperature moderately can significantly speed up the ageing reaction rate, while having hardly any influence on the original ageing mechanism (Bank, Gentry, Thompson, & Russell, 2003; Huang & Aboutaha, 2010; Spelter, Bielak, Will, & Hegger, 2018).

In order to quantify the internal relationship between temperature setup and accelerated ageing rate, Arrhenius Equation (Laidler, 1984) has been adopted in existing studies to guide the relevant experimental design. Since Arrhenius Equation was proposed, it has been widely used in scientific research including mass diffusion, chemical reactions, creep relaxation and long-term material degradation (So, Choi, Seo, Seo, & So, 2014; Tant, McManus, & Roger, 1995; Zhang, Han, Guo, & Sun, 2015). Arrhenius Equation has a close relationship to molecular reaction dynamics. The macroscopic reaction rate indicated by the Arrhenius Equation is in accordance with the result of intermolecular collision frequency and interaction (Kovalenko & Dobryakov, 2013). With temperature

rising, the intermolecular collision frequency goes up and the intermolecular interaction turns intense. This phenomenon interprets the dependence of ageing reaction rate on the ambient temperature at the micro level.

As regards the temperature selection, existing literature indicates that the accelerated ageing treatment with overly high temperature is more likely to change the degradation reaction mechanism and causes the underestimate of material durability (Ascione, Caron, Godonou, & Ijselmuijden, 2016; Ksouri & Haddar, 2018; Robert, Wang, Cousin, & Benmokrane, 2010). In view of this, 60 °C is usually adopted by relevant studies as the acceleration temperature which is also recommended by the current durability testing standard such as ACI 440.3R-12 (American Concrete Institute, 2012) and CAN/CSA S806 (Canadian Standards Association, 2021). Many published experimental results have proved that such a temperature is efficient to facilitate the ageing process and observe the degradation phenomenon of FRP material in a short period (Al-Lami, D’Antino, & Colombi, 2020; Chen, Davalos, & Ray, 2006). Therefore, the accelerated ageing approach used in the present study decides 60 °C as the immersion temperature to age carbon fibre strand reinforced mortar (CFSRM) specimens.

EXPERIMENT SETUP

A custom-made insulated curing tank, as shown in Figure 1, was built for carrying out the accelerated ageing test. A digital thermostatic controller was attached to the tank, as shown in Figure 1b), which worked as an automatic switch of heating and keeps the seawater temperature fluctuating within the range of 60 ± 0.5 °C.

Figure 1 Elevated-temperature insulated seawater curing tank: a) stainless steel curing tank; b) digital thermostatic controller.

Another control group of specimens was prepared alongside, which were immersed in 20 °C normal temperature seawater for the same duration as for the elevated-temperature treated specimens.

In general, the accelerated ageing period varies from 7 to 240 days (Nepomuceno, Sena-Cruz, Correia, & D’Antino, 2021). For fibre composite materials, existing literature indicates that the material degradation slows down with time (Silva, Fonseca, & Biscaia, 2014; Wang et al., 2017a), which is more distinct under high temperature accelerated ageing process (Chen et al., 2006; Uthaman et al., 2020). In order to optimise the experimental work, various duration intervals should be adopted. In this study, durations of 30, 60, 120 and 240 days were used for both 20 °C and 60 °C test groups. Based on the aforementioned experimental variable setup, each test with a unique set of experimental variables was repeated three times to ensure the reliable results which were collected from the same test group including three specimens after the same ageing conditioning. The specimen labels used herein indicate the purpose and the conditioning method of specimens as follows: “P” denotes the pull-out test; “60C” or “20C” means the seawater immersion temperature; “30d, 60d, 120d, 240d” represents the ageing treatment duration; the last number in the label symbolises the serial number of specimens conditioned in the same way. In this way, the specimens used for 20 °C test groups are named by P20C-30d-1, 2, 3; P20C-60d-1, 2, 3; P20C-120d-1, 2, 3 and P20C-240d-1, 2, 3 respectively. The specimens used for 60

°C test groups are named by P60C-30d-1, 2, 3; P60C-60d-1, 2, 3; P60C-120d-1, 2, 3 and P60C-240d-1, 2, 3 respectively. Figure 2 shows the overall specimens for the interfacial degradation study.

Figure 2 Specimens prepared for CFSRM degradation investigation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pull-out performance of CFSRM exposed to elevated temperature accelerated ageing

Figure 3 displays all pull-out tested CFSRM specimens after elevated-temperature accelerated ageing treatment at 60 °C, from left to right in chronological order of ageing duration. CFS pull-out failure mode, namely the interfacial debonding failure between CFS and mortar, was found for all specimens, and little difference was found among different ageing periods. That is, the fibre reinforcement of all CFSRM specimens presented here was pulled out from the mortar substrate after the test.

Figure 3 Tested CFSRM specimens exposed to elevated-temperature accelerated ageing of seawater immersion at 60 °C

Figure 4 shows the pull-out test results of CFSRM specimens after 30, 60, 120 and 240 days of elevated-temperature accelerated ageing respectively. A gradual decline in the residual pull-out performance of CFSRM has been found. The decrease in the peak pull-out force becomes more evident with the increase of the ageing period. Additionally, the ascending stage of the pull-out force-displacement curve becomes more nonlinear with a longer degradation duration, which suggests that the interfacial bonding between CFS and mortar is more likely to lose the integrity under longer exposure time.

Although the test results for all specimens complied with the pull-out failure type, it should be noted that the discreteness and the randomness still existed in the test results. As shown in Figure 4b), the peak pull-out force on the blue curve (P60C-60d-2) has a lower value than others. It means that the interfacial debonding failure of this specimen occurred earlier than other specimens. The CFS/SM bond of P60C-60d-2 is weaker compared with P60C-60d-1 or P60C-60d-3. Such a lower pull-out performance may result from the specimen making process or the experimental operation process. As

shown in Figure 4c), the pull-out curve of the green one (P60C-120d-3) has a strange shape with fluctuation in half way. The long-term ageing treatment damaged the integrity of adhesive interface between CFS and SM, leading to the problem of uneven shear stress transfer from SM to CFS when the specimen was acted upon by a force (Davalos, Chen, & Ray, 2012b). Consequently, partial fibre filaments at the outermost CFS were prone to the early rupture during the loading process. Then the pull-out force experienced a sudden drop at its ascending stage as the interfacial shear stress was redistributed along the remaining continuous fibres. Owing to the fact that the interfacial bond still worked by this moment, the pull-out force continued to go up until reaching the peak point which represented the maximum pull-out force the specimen could sustain.

(a) Day 30

(b) Day 60

(c) Day 120

(d) Day 240

Figure 4 Pull-out curves of CFSRM specimens under ageing treatment at 60 °C.

Pull-out performance of CFSRM under normal service condition

Figure 5 displays all tested specimens from left to right in chronological order of 20 °C conditioning duration. Little difference in the failure mode of pull-out has been found when compared with those in 60 °C test group. It indicates that the reinforcement rupture does not happen during the test and the interfacial failure controls the pull-out test results for all specimens in this study.

Figure 5 Tested CFSRC specimens exposed to the normal service condition of seawater immersion at 20 °C

The pull-out force-displacement curves of CFSRM specimens after 30, 60, 120 and 240 days of treatment under normal service conditions are shown in Figure 6. Unlike the 60 °C test group, no distinct difference of test results can be observed within the first 120 days of treatment. The variation trend in the peak pull-out force indicates that the deterioration of adhesive interface between CFS and SM under the normal service condition at 20 °C is much slower than the accelerated ageing condition at 60 °C. Consequently, specimens from 20 °C test group maintain the higher pull-out resistance than 60 °C test group when the long-term conditioning is ended at the 240th day. Furthermore, linear increase in the ascent stage of the pull-out curve has been found among all conditioning time. Compared with specimens from 60 °C test group, environmental conditioning of immersion at 20 °C is deemed less likely to damage the interfacial integrity, which is in agreement with what reported in the literature (Tatar & Hamilton, 2016; Wang et al., 2017a).

(a) Day 30

(b) Day 60

(c) Day 120

(d) Day 240

Figure 6 Pull-out curves of CFSRM specimens at 20 °C.

Comparison between the two immersion conditions

Table 1 summarises all pull-out test results of the specimens under both elevated-temperature and normal temperature environment. The percentage of residual performance shown in Table 1 is defined as the ratio of the current pull-out force to 1.95 kN that represents the initial pull-out force of CFSRM specimen before any exposure, as derived in (Ji, 2023).

Table 1 The results summary of pull-out test with CFSRM specimens.

Specimen name	Pull-out force (kN)	Residual performance (%)	Mean value (kN)	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation (%)
P60C-30d-1	1.93	98.9			
P60C-30d-2	1.72	88.2	1.88	0.13	7.2
P60C-30d-3	1.97	101.1			
P60C-60d-1	1.66	85.2			
P60C-60d-2	1.42	72.7	1.64	0.21	12.8
P60C-60d-3	1.84	94.2			
P60C-120d-1	1.01	51.9			
P60C-120d-2	1.12	57.4	1.02	0.09	9.1
P60C-120d-3	0.94	48.0			
P60C-240d-1	1.30	66.8			
P60C-240d-2	1.04	53.5	1.15	0.14	12.1
P60C-240d-3	1.09	55.9			
P20C-30d-1	2.07	106.2			
P20C-30d-2	1.92	98.5	1.95	0.12	5.9
P20C-30d-3	1.85	94.5			
P20C-60d-1	1.97	100.8			
P20C-60d-2	2.10	107.4	2.02	0.07	3.4
P20C-60d-3	1.99	101.9			
P20C-120d-1	1.76	90.0			
P20C-120d-2	1.97	101.0	1.92	0.14	7.5
P20C-120d-3	2.03	103.9			
P20C-240d-1	1.54	79.1			
P20C-240d-2	1.86	95.1	1.71	0.16	9.2
P20C-240d-3	1.74	89.3			

Figure 7 plots the reduction in pull-out force of all specimens. The descending trend between the 60 °C condition and 20 °C condition starts to distinguish from the 30th day onwards. The average retention

of pull-out force drops to 58.7% (1.15 kN) under accelerated ageing by the end of the experimental duration, in comparison to 87.8% (1.71 kN) for specimens at 20 °C. When the specimens are under 60 °C condition, the pull-out force reduces steadily to its lowest value at the 120th day, and increases slightly afterwards. When the specimens are under 20 °C condition, the pull-out force fluctuates slightly in the first 60 days, since then it reduces monotonically until the end of the test. The slight increase in the pull-out force of specimens under either 60 °C or 20 °C condition could be related to the continuous hydration of the cementitious materials, especially PFA, which has been found to contribute to long-term strength in concrete (Hwang, Noguchi, & Tomosawa, 2004). However, further studies will be needed to prove this hypothesis, as the effect of continuous hydration has been neglected in this study.

Figure 7 Reductions in pull-out force of CFSRM exposed to accelerated ageing condition and normal service condition.

CONCLUSIONS

In accordance with Arrhenius Law, CFSRM specimens exposed to 60 °C accelerated ageing treatment along with the control group at 20 °C are used to conduct pull-out tests in order to measure the retention of pull-out force after the accelerated ageing treatment. Test results show that the pull-out performance of specimens after 240 days of accelerated ageing has an obvious reduction, to 58.7% of the pull-out force without ageing treatment. Meanwhile, little change is found under normal service condition, retaining 87.8% of the pull-out force by the end of the test.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is found in its entirety in (Ji, 2023).

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